

Integrating GIS and Geoportals for Sustainable Beach Management: A Comprehensive Approach in M'diq

Ayoub LAHLOUH^{1,*}, Nisserine BEN DRISS¹

¹ Regional Planning and Territorial Development Laboratory, Department of Geography, Abdelmalek Essaâdi University, Tetouan, Morocco

Corresponding author: *ayoub.lahlouh@etu.uae.ac.ma

Abstract

This study explores the application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in enhancing the management and development of M'diq's beaches. Employing a comprehensive strategy, the research focuses on the formation of a management committee, extensive data collection, and the creation of an innovative geoportal. This platform integrates detailed maps, environmental data, and economic license statistics for amenities such as parasols, jet skis, and kiosks, providing a multifaceted view of beach management.

Key findings highlight the diversity of amenities and the critical importance of water quality, with insights drawn from the National Laboratory for Studies and Pollution Monitoring. The study underscores the need for regular environmental monitoring and adaptive management strategies, offering significant implications for sustainable coastal management. The methodologies and insights presented not only contribute to the field of GIS and environmental management but also provide a valuable framework for other coastal regions aiming to balance ecological preservation with economic and recreational activities.

Keywords: GIS (Geographic Information System); Geoportal; Beach Management, Decision-making, M'diq, Economic Licenses.

Introduction

Beaches are not only natural treasures but also vital components of the local economy and environment. Effective management of these areas is crucial, especially in regions like M'diq, where coastal landscapes play a significant role in community life and tourism. The integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in beach management has emerged as a transformative approach, offering new possibilities for sustainable and efficient coastal stewardship (Rudianto et al., 2023). Central to this integration is the use of a geoportal, a web-based platform that aggregates, manages, and disseminates geographic data and tools, facilitating real-time access and decision-making (Maguire & Longley, 2005).

Recent advancements in GIS and remote sensing technologies have significantly enhanced the capabilities of environmental and geographical management. For instance, Abdelhaleem et al. (2021) demonstrated the application of remote sensing and GIS in irrigation water management under water scarcity conditions in Egypt, highlighting the potential of these technologies in managing natural (Abdelhaleem et al., 2021). Similarly, the work of Bai and Pan (2022) on the construction method of historical geographic information systems based on mobile networks underscores the evolving nature of GIS applications in various geographical contexts (Bai & Pan, 2022).

In the context of transportation and infrastructure, the implementation of GIS for road maintenance management, as explored by Saepudin et al. (2022) in Bandung District, illustrates the system's versatility in managing and improving essential services (Saepudin et al., 2022). Furthermore, the applications of marine GIS in ocean surveying, as

discussed by Zhang, provide insights into the broader implications of GIS in marine and coastal environments (Shu Zhang, 2023).

The objective of this study is to delve into how GIS technology, particularly through the use of a geoportal, is revolutionizing beach management and promoting sustainable coastal development, with a particular focus on the beaches of M'diq. Through a detailed analysis of the M'diq scenario, this research intends to offer an in-depth perspective on how GIS contributes to improving beach management strategies, safeguarding the environment, and bolstering the local economy. This study aims to bridge the gap between technological potential and practical application, demonstrating the transformative power of GIS and geoportals in coastal management.

1 Research area

M'diq is a collectivity located on the Tetouan coast in Morocco (**Fig. 1**), the population of this collectivity has fluctuated over time, growing from 2,412 people in 1960 to 56,130 people in 2014. (Haut Commissariat au Plan, 2014) This increase has provided valuable human resources to support the development of the urban area of M'diq at all stages. However, the slowing growth rate and varying patterns of growth raise questions about the accuracy of population movement data and the demographic future of the area.

In recent times, M'diq's population has expanded swiftly, fueled by high birth rates and migration from rural zones in Morocco. This rapid expansion has led to challenges for local authorities, affecting public services and the balance between economic progress and environmental conservation. The coastal zones, like those of M'diq, are among the most threatened by increased flood occurrences and rapid urbanization. The impact of

floods particularly affects densely populated areas, making exposure to floods a significant societal issue as the region experiences a decrease in average annual rainfall and an increase in average annual temperature. Despite the implementation of new policies to mitigate the effects of rural migration and promote economic growth through tourism and free-zone industries, these areas' vulnerability to climate change remains a concern (Satour et al., 2021).

Fig. 1. M'diq Collectivity

2 Problem Statement

Despite the critical role of beaches in environmental, economic, and social spheres, their management in M'diq, a coastal town renowned for its picturesque beaches, faces significant challenges. These challenges not only impact the environmental sustainability and recreational quality of the beaches but also the overall well-being of the local community and ecosystem. The primary issues include:

Environmental Sustainability: Beaches in M'diq are delicate ecosystems. Mismanagement can lead to severe consequences like erosion, pollution, and loss of biodiversity, further exacerbated by increasing tourist activities and urban development.

Resource Allocation: Efficiently allocating resources for beach maintenance, safety, and amenities is a complex task. The dynamic nature of beach environments, influenced by seasonal changes and varying tourist influx, requires adaptive and informed management strategies.

Data Management and Accessibility: Traditional methods of beach management often rely on outdated or static data, hindering effective decision-making. The lack of real-time, comprehensive data about beach conditions poses significant hurdles in responding to environmental and recreational needs promptly.

Stakeholder Engagement: Sustainable beach management requires active engagement from local communities, tourists, and various stakeholders. However, there is often a disconnect in communication and collaboration among these groups, leading to ineffective or unpopular management strategies.

Regulatory Compliance and Policy Implementation: The multifaceted nature of beach ecosystems and the variety of interests involved make adhering to environmental regulations and implementing policies effectively a challenging task.

The integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in beach management presents a promising solution to these challenges. GIS can provide real-time, accurate data, aiding in environmental monitoring, resource allocation, and stakeholder engagement. However, the application of GIS in this context is not without its challenges. These include technical limitations, data accuracy concerns, and the need for specialized skills to interpret and utilize the data effectively.

This paper aims to explore these challenges in the context of M'diq's beaches and examine how GIS technology can be leveraged to address them. It will delve into the potential of GIS to revolutionize beach management and contribute to the sustainable development of coastal areas, while also addressing the practical considerations and barriers to its implementation.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology for this study on the application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in beach management in M'diq involved several key steps, utilizing a range of data sources and technological tools.

Fig. 2. A Systematic Workflow for Beach Management Using GIS Technology

The primary goal was to create a comprehensive geodatabase that would facilitate the effective division and management of the beaches into economic and public areas, in accordance with the standards set by the joint directive of the Ministry of Interior and the Ministry of Equipment, Transport, Logistics, and Water (Ministry of Interior & Ministry of Equipment, Transport, Logistics, and Water, 2018). The following outlines the materials and methods used in this study.

3.1 Committee formation

A committee was formed to oversee the division of approximately nine beaches in M'diq (Fig. 3) into economic and public zones, adhering to the standards set by the joint directive.

Fig. 3. M'diq Beach Areas' Locations

3.2 Data Collection

- **Aerial Photography and Open Street Map:** Initial data on the geographical features and layout of the beaches were gathered.
- **Field Data Gathering:** Using the MapIt app on tablets, data was collected from the field, including locations of facilities such as restrooms, police stations, and other relevant beach infrastructure.
- **Surveys with Commercial License Holders:** Conducted to gather insights for the accurate division of the beaches.
- **Data Cleaning and Processing:** Using ArcGIS Pro, the collected data underwent a cleaning process to ensure accuracy and relevance, with attributes added to the features.

3.3 Division of Beach Areas

Effective beach management requires a strategic division of areas to balance public access, economic activities, and environmental conservation. This section outlines the

systematic approach adopted in allocating different zones within the beaches of M'diq. The division is designed to optimize the use of beach space, ensuring that both public enjoyment and economic ventures can coexist sustainably. Key aspects of this division include designating areas for public use, managing economic activities, and regulating specific amenities and services. Each aspect is carefully considered to maintain the beach's integrity while accommodating the needs of visitors and stakeholders (Fig. 4).

- **Public Area:** 80% of each beach was designated for public use.
- **Economic Activities Area:** 20% of each beach was allocated for economic activities.
- **Parasol Management:** Each stakeholder was allocated 8 parasols, each covering 3 square meters, with a 1-meter empty space between parasols.
- **Kiosk Allocation:** Permitted only on specific beaches and exclusively available to established stakeholders.
- **Pedalos and Jet Ski Regulations:** Allowed only on certain beaches, with specific restrictions.

Fig. 4. Detailed Flowchart of Beach Area Division Methodology in M'diq

3.4 Geoportal Design

- **Map Creation and Design:** Custom maps for each beach were created with detailed information about the divided areas, designed for print purposes.
- **Beach Map Content as per Plan Requirements:** The map includes sensitive areas, concession spaces, kiosks, parking areas, accessible entrances, sanitary blocks, first aid centers, environmental information centers, entertainment areas, sports activity areas, waste disposal facilities, civil protection facilities, watch-towers, signage, and information boards.
- **Development of the Beach Geoportal:** A beach geoportal system was designed using ArcGIS Experience Builder and made public.

3.5 Publishing the Geoportal

- **Publishing the Geodatabase:** The geodatabase was published to ArcGIS Online for further analysis and sharing.
- **QR Code Integration:** QR codes linking to the online geoportal were created and integrated into the printed maps.
- **Information Display on Beaches:** Billboards displaying maps and additional information were erected at each beach.

4 Results and Discussions

4.1 Overview of Beach Characteristics

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the physical and structural characteristics of the studied beaches, with a particular focus on M'diq city beach. A critical aspect of this study was the application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to divide and manage M'diq beach into economic and public areas, adhering to the standards set by the joint directive of the Ministry of Interior and the Ministry of Equipment, Transport, Logistics, and Water, dated May 17, 2018.

To illustrate the practical application of these criteria and the effectiveness of our GIS-based approach, we have included a detailed map design of M'diq city beach (**Fig. 5**). This map serves as an example of the meticulous planning and structured approach

required to meet the regulatory standards while catering to the needs of beachgoers and preserving the natural environment.

Fig. 5. Detailed Map Design of M'diq City Beach Based on Ministry Criteria

The map presents a comprehensive layout of M'diq City Beach, showcasing how the ministry's criteria have been translated into a practical and functional design using GIS technology. It highlights the designated areas for public access, commercial activities, and environmental protection. The map also includes the location of amenities such as access points, kiosks, sanitary facilities, and recreational zones, all arranged according to the prescribed guidelines. This visual representation demonstrates the effective integration of regulatory requirements with the aim of providing a safe, enjoyable, and sustainable beach experience.

The inclusion of this map design exemplifies the application of regulatory criteria in beach management and underscores the importance of strategic planning in developing

and maintaining beach areas that meet both visitor expectations and environmental standards.

4.1.1 Beach Dimensions

We analyzed several beaches, each with unique dimensions that contribute to their character and capacity. The lengths of the beaches varied significantly, with beach M'diq City being the longest at 1.8 km and beach Qasr Al Rimal being the shortest at 350 m. The average width of the beaches was generally around 50 m, providing ample space for recreational activities and visitors. These dimensions are crucial for understanding the potential of each beach and planning for appropriate facilities and services (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Division of Beach Areas in M'diq

Beach Name	Length	Total Area	Area for Seasonal Commercial Activities	Public Area
M'diq City	1.8 km	6ha 95a 34ca	1ha 39a 06.8ca	5ha 56a 27.2ca
Kabilla	1 km	4ha 16a 12ca	83a 22.4ca	3ha 32a 89.6ca
Qasr Al Rimal	350 m	1ha 78a 10ca	35a 62ca	1ha 42a 48ca
Saniat Al Torres	400 m	1ha 71a 86ca	34a 37.2ca	1ha 37a 48.8ca
Marina Puerto	1.2 km	4ha 41a 52ca	88a 30.4ca	3ha 53a 21.6ca
Marina Asmir	600 m	4ha 16a 03ca	83a 20.6ca	3ha 32a 82.4ca
Marina Beach	360 m	1ha 46a 08ca	29a 21.6ca	1ha 16a 86.4ca
Restingua	460 m	8ha 37a 73ca	1ha 67a 54.6ca	6ha 70a 18.4ca
Almina	605 m	7ha 42a 47ca	1ha 48a 49.4ca	5ha 93a 97.6ca

4.1.2 Capacity and Attendance

The capacity of each beach was estimated based on its dimensions and the typical space required per visitor. For instance, beach M'diq, with its extensive length and favorable width, has a capacity to accommodate up to 10,000 people (M'diq Collectivity, 2021)¹. However, the actual daily attendance was not consistently available for all beaches, indicating a gap in data that could be vital for effective management and planning. Where data was available, it provided insight into the popularity and usage patterns of the beaches, which is essential for resource allocation and managing environmental impact.

4.1.3 Physical Characteristics

The physical characteristics of each beach, including the type of sand, slope, and natural features such as dunes and vegetation, were noted. These characteristics are important for understanding the natural environment of the beach and planning for its preservation and maintenance. For example, beaches with delicate dune systems may require special protective measures to prevent erosion and habitat loss.

4.1.4 Accessibility and Surrounding Infrastructure

The accessibility of each beach was assessed based on the number of access points and their suitability for various visitors, including those with special needs. The surrounding infrastructure, such as roads, public transport links, and proximity to residential or

¹ This information is derived from the 'Application File for Obtaining the Blue Flag Label 2021,' a confidential document provided by the M'diq Collectivity.

commercial areas, was also considered. This information is crucial for planning visitor access and ensuring that beaches are inclusive and welcoming to all.

4.2 Amenities and Infrastructure

4.2.1 Access and Parking

Our study revealed a varied number of access points across the beaches, with some like beach Marina Puerto offering as many as 9 entry points, enhancing accessibility for visitors. However, some beaches had unspecified access points, indicating a potential area for improvement in visitor accessibility and flow management. Parking facilities also varied, with some beaches like Beach Restingua and Marina Asmir providing 2 parking areas, while others, such as Beach Kabilla, had none. The availability and capacity of parking are crucial for visitor convenience and managing the influx of beachgoers, especially during peak seasons.

4.2.2 Sanitary Facilities and First Aid

The provision of sanitary facilities such as WC and showers is essential for visitor comfort and maintaining beach hygiene. Our findings show a range in the number of sanitary facilities available, with Beach Almina offering as many as 10. The presence of first aid centers and civil protection locals is vital for ensuring visitor safety and providing immediate care in case of emergencies. However, this study found that many beaches lacked specified first aid centers, highlighting an area for potential development in visitor safety services.

4.2.3 Safety Measures

Safety on the beaches is of paramount importance. Watchtowers, or miradors, are critical for lifeguard surveillance and ensuring swimmer safety. Our results indicate that some beaches, like Beach Almina, are well-equipped with up to 7 watchtowers. Additionally, the presence of police stations contributes to overall security and order on the beach. The study found that police presence varied across the beaches, with some having up to 3 stations and others none.

4.2.4 Signage and Information

Proper signage and information boards are crucial in guiding visitors, providing safety instructions, and offering educational content about the beach environment. These boards are essential for informing visitors about various aspects such as safety protocols, beach design plans, utility contact numbers, and water quality indicators. Consistent and clear signage across all beaches is crucial for ensuring visitor safety and enhancing their overall experience.

In addition to the textual description of the signage and information boards available at the beaches, we have included an image of a typical signage tableboard found at one of the studied beaches (**Fig. 6**). This tableboard serves as an example of how vital information, rules, and safety guidelines are communicated to beachgoers, illustrating the importance of effective and informative signage in maintaining a safe and enjoyable beach environment.

Fig. 6. Example of Signage Tableboard at M'diq City Beach

4.3 Recreational and Commercial Features

In the pursuit of sustainable beach management and to enhance the visitor experience, a structured approach to permitting recreational and commercial amenities is crucial. This section provides an overview of the licensed amenities allowed on various beaches in M'diq and surrounding areas. The data reflects the balance between promoting tourism and leisure activities while ensuring environmental protection and public safety.

The graph presented in this section (**Fig. 7**), serves as a comprehensive summary of the types and quantities of amenities permitted on each beach. This includes jet skis, parasols, pedal boats, and kiosks each representing a facet of the beach experience and economic activity.

Fig. 7. Permitted Recreational and Commercial Amenities by Beach (August 2023)

Understanding the permitted amenities is vital for multiple stakeholders, including local government bodies, environmental agencies, beachgoers, and business owners. For local authorities and environmental agencies, this data aids in planning, regulation enforcement, and environmental impact assessments. Beachgoers benefit from knowing the available facilities and activities, enhancing their overall experience. Simultaneously, business owners and potential investors gain insight into the commercial opportunities and regulations within these coastal areas (**Fig. 8**).

Fig. 8. Interventions of the M'diq collectivity in managing M'diq city Beach

The following detailed analysis of specific amenities—parasols, jet skis, kiosks and pedal boats—illustrates how these various interests converge in the management and enjoyment of beach resources. Each amenity not only contributes to the economic and recreational appeal of the beaches but also reflects the careful consideration of environmental and safety concerns in their regulation and distribution.

4.3.1 Parasols

Parasols are essential for providing shade and comfort to beachgoers. Our findings indicate a significant variation in the number of parasols available across the beaches. Almina beach leads with 50 parasols, contributing to a total of 242 across all studied beaches. This variation reflects the differing capacities, and visitor needs at each location.

The distribution and regulation of parasols are carefully managed to ensure that they enhance the beach experience while respecting the natural environment and other users' space.

4.3.2 Jet Skis

Jet skis offer an exciting recreational activity for visitors. While not as widely available as other amenities, there are a total of 4 jet skis across the beaches, with Marina Beach offering 2. The controlled number reflects a balance between providing fun activities and ensuring safety and environmental protection. The regulation of jet skis is particularly important, as their use must be carefully managed to prevent accidents and minimize disturbances to beachgoers.

4.3.3 Pedal Boats

Pedal boats are a popular and family-friendly beach activity. The study found a total of 52 pedal boats across the beaches, with beach Almina providing 14, the highest among them. Like parasols and jet skis, the availability of pedal boats is a managed amenity, reflecting considerations of safety, environmental impact, and the capacity of each beach. They offer a leisurely and environmentally friendly way to enjoy the water, appealing to visitors of all ages.

4.3.4 Kiosks

Kiosks serve various needs, from food and drinks to beach equipment rentals, and are a vital component of the beach economy. A total of 31 kiosks were reported, with Beach

Restingua having the highest number at 10. These establishments not only enhance the beach experience by providing essential services and conveniences but also support local entrepreneurs and contribute to the local economy. The presence and regulation of kiosks are carefully considered to ensure they meet visitor needs while maintaining the beach's aesthetic and environmental standards.

4.3.5 Overall Recreational and Commercial Offerings.

The total count of amenities, including parasols, jet skis, pedal boats, and kiosks, reflects the recreational and commercial capacity of the beaches. With 329 features combined, the beaches offer a range of activities and services catering to different preferences and needs. This diversity is crucial for attracting and satisfying a broad spectrum of visitors, contributing to the overall appeal and sustainability of the beaches. It demonstrates a commitment to providing a comprehensive and enjoyable beach experience while ensuring the responsible use and preservation of natural resources.

4.4 Environmental Management

4.4.1 Sand Cleaning Practices

Effective sand cleaning is crucial for maintaining the aesthetic appeal and ecological health of the beach. Our study observed various approaches to sand cleaning across the beaches, with some employing mechanical methods and others relying on manual labor. The choice of method often reflects a balance between efficiency, cost, and environmental impact. Mechanical cleaning allows for rapid and thorough removal of debris but can

sometimes disrupt the beach's natural state. In contrast, manual cleaning is less invasive but more labor-intensive. The frequency and method of sand cleaning are essential factors in preserving the beach's natural beauty and providing a clean, safe environment for visitors.

4.4.2 Trash Disposal Facilities

Proper trash disposal is vital for preventing pollution and maintaining the natural beauty of the beaches. Our findings indicate a range in the number of trash bins available across the beaches, with some, like Beach Restingua, providing as many as 18 bins. The capacity of these bins, often 160 liters, is suitable for high-traffic areas, helping to keep the beaches clean and enjoyable for all. Regular collection and maintenance of these facilities are crucial for their effectiveness. The study also highlights the importance of visitor education and signage to encourage responsible trash disposal.

4.4.3 Environmental Protection Zones

Some beaches have designated areas to protect sensitive ecosystems, such as dunes, vegetation, and marine life. These zones are critical for preserving biodiversity and the natural beauty of the beach environment. Our study notes the presence or absence of such protected areas and any measures taken to enforce their protection, such as fencing, signage, or restricted access. The management of these zones is a key aspect of sustainable beach management, balancing recreational use with conservation needs.

4.4.4 Water Quality Monitoring

Continuous water quality monitoring is crucial for ensuring the safety and enjoyment of beachgoers, as well as for maintaining the health of marine ecosystems. In our study, we referred to the water quality assessments reported by the "National Laboratory for Studies and Pollution Monitoring". This report provided ratings for various monitoring stations along the beaches, reflecting the results of comprehensive tests conducted by the laboratory. These tests evaluated several factors, including bacterial levels, pollution, and other critical indicators of water quality (Ministère de la Transition Énergétique, et du Développement Durable, Département de Développement Durable, 2023). The following summary encapsulates the key findings as reported by the laboratory (**Table 2**)

Table 2. Water Quality Ratings at Beach Monitoring Stations 2023

Beach Name	Station	Location Description	X Coord	Y Coord	Water Quality Rating
M'diq	S1	North of the port breakwater	507155	564654	Good
	S9	Opposite the Golden Beach Hotel	506920	564857	Good
	S18	300m North of the Golden Beach Hotel	506756	565144	Excellent
	S27	Opposite the Holiday Hotel (Northernmost point)	506478	565972	Excellent
Kabilla	S1	Middle of the beach	505548	569132	Good
	S2	200m South of S1	505622	568896	Sufficient

Qasr Al Rimal	S1	Middle of the beach	505410	569945	Data not available
	S2	100m to the right of S1 (Formerly S2 of Sania Torres)	505419	569791	Excellent
	S3	250m West of S1 (Formerly S1 of Sania Torres)	505374	570038	Excellent

Variable Water Quality Across Beaches: The table indicates a range of water quality conditions across different beaches and even within different areas of the same beach. This variability highlights the complex nature of coastal ecosystems and the influence of various factors like proximity to urban areas, natural currents, and human activities (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Overall Water Quality Distribution

Areas of Excellence: Stations with 'Excellent' ratings, such as S18 and S27 in M'diq and several in Qasr Al Rimal, are indicative of pristine water conditions. These areas likely benefit from effective environmental protection measures, lower pollution levels,

and possibly favorable natural conditions. They set a benchmark for other areas and demonstrate the potential for high-quality beach environments.

Need for Improvement: The 'Sufficient' rating at Kabila's S2 station suggests that while the water quality may not pose immediate health risks, it does not meet the highest standards. This rating serves as an indicator for potential issues or emerging threats that require attention, possibly calling for more stringent management practices or pollution mitigation efforts.

Importance of Comprehensive Monitoring: The absence of data for certain stations, such as S1 in Qasr Al Rimal, underscores the importance of consistent and comprehensive monitoring. Regular data collection is crucial for understanding trends, identifying potential problems early, and ensuring that all areas meet safety and environmental standards.

Implications for Stakeholders: The varied water quality ratings have direct implications for different stakeholders:

- **Local Authorities and Environmental Agencies:** Need to focus on areas with lower ratings or missing data to improve and maintain high standards. This might involve pollution control, infrastructure improvements, or stricter regulation enforcement.
- **Beachgoers:** Can make informed decisions about where to visit based on water quality, which can influence their safety and enjoyment.
- **Business Owners:** Particularly those in tourism and recreation, should be aware of the water quality as it can impact visitor satisfaction and, consequently, their business.

Opportunity for Community Engagement: The table can serve as a tool for engaging the local community and visitors in conservation efforts. By understanding the current state of their beaches, individuals can be more proactive in maintaining cleanliness, reporting pollution, and supporting environmental initiatives.

Baseline for Future Actions: The data provides a baseline for tracking changes over time. By regularly updating this information, authorities can assess the effectiveness of their management strategies, adapt to new challenges, and continuously work towards improving the overall quality of the beach environment.

4.5 Geoportal Creating and Publishing

The creation and publication of a geoportal represent the culmination of extensive data collection, analysis, and design efforts aimed at providing a comprehensive and user-friendly platform for beach management and public information (Maguire & Longley, 2005). This section outlines the key steps and considerations involved in bringing the geoportal from concept to reality, making it an accessible and valuable resource for various stakeholders (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Beach Management and Utilization Geoportal Interface

Before delving into the specifics of the geoportal's functionality, it's crucial to understand the foundational elements that make such a detailed and user-centric platform possible. A comprehensive geodatabase was developed, encapsulating a wide array of data

concerning M'diq's beaches. This geodatabase serves as the backbone of our geoportal and provides a visually appealing and intuitive representation of complex data (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. ArcGIS Pro Visualization of M'diq Beach Data

The visualization presented above is a direct representation of the geodatabase's capabilities. It emphasizes aspects such as zoning, amenities, bus and taxi stations, access points, green spaces, and more. By providing a clear and detailed visual representation, stakeholders can better understand the spatial distribution and management needs of M'diq's beaches. This level of detail is not only crucial for immediate management tasks but also serves as a critical resource for long-term planning and development.

With the geodatabase and its visualization capabilities established, we can now explore how these elements integrate into the broader framework of the geoportal. The following sections will delve into the geoportal's specific features, its user-centric design, and how

it leverages the comprehensive data and visual insights provided by the geodatabase to serve its users effectively.

In the realm of modern beach management and environmental stewardship, the development of a geoportal represents a significant advancement. This geoportal, specifically designed for the beaches of M'diq, serves as a centralized digital platform that facilitates the access, analysis, and sharing of geographic information. It is a pivotal tool in the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) technology with public accessibility and environmental management (Maguire & Longley, 2005).

4.5.1 Purpose and Functionality

The primary purpose of the geoportal is to provide an interactive and user-friendly interface for various stakeholders, including local authorities, environmentalists, tourists, and researchers. It offers a comprehensive view of M'diq's coastal areas, combining detailed geographic data with practical information. The geoportal is designed to enhance decision-making processes, promote sustainable beach management practices, and foster greater public awareness of the coastal environment.

4.5.2 User-Centric Design

At the heart of the geoportal's development was a focus on user experience. The interface was crafted to be intuitive and easily navigable, ensuring that users of varying technical backgrounds can access and understand the information presented. Key features include interactive maps, searchable databases, and user-friendly tools for data visualization.

4.5.3 Integration of GIS and Web Technologies

The geoportal represents a seamless integration of GIS capabilities with modern web technologies (He et al., 2012). This integration allows for real-time data processing and visualization, offering users up-to-date information on beach conditions, environmental quality, and available amenities. The platform's backend is powered by robust GIS software, enabling sophisticated spatial analysis and data management.

4.5.4 Accessibility and Interactivity

Accessibility is a cornerstone of the geoportal's design. It is accessible via various devices, including desktop computers, tablets, and smartphones, ensuring that users can access vital information from anywhere (He et al., 2012). Interactivity is another key feature, allowing users to engage with the data through features like zooming in on specific beach areas, toggling between different data layers, and accessing detailed information about specific points of interest.

4.5.5 Data Richness and Diversity

The geoportal serves as a comprehensive repository of diverse data sets, offering an extensive range of information that extends beyond mere geographical details. It's designed to provide users with a holistic view of beach management and economic activities. The data hosted on the geoportal includes, but is not limited to:

4.5.6 Detailed Maps

These maps clearly delineate zones designated for commercial activities and public use. The demarcations are based on the criteria set forth by the Ministry of Interior and the Ministry of Equipment, Transport, Logistics, and Water, ensuring adherence to regulatory standards and guidelines.

4.5.7 Environmental Data

Users can access a variety of environmental information, including water quality ratings and the locations of protected natural areas. This data is crucial for understanding the ecological health of the beaches and surrounding environments.

4.5.8 Infrastructure and Amenity Information

The geoportal provides detailed information on essential infrastructure and amenities. This includes the locations of restrooms, lifeguard stations, parking areas, and access points, all of which are vital for ensuring a safe and enjoyable beach experience.

4.5.9 Statistical Data on Economic Licenses

A significant feature of the geoportal is its comprehensive statistical data on economic licenses by type, such as parasols, jet skis, and kiosks. This information provides valuable insights into the economic activities and commercial landscape of the beaches. Users can analyze the distribution and prevalence of different types of licenses, aiding in economic planning and policymaking.

4.5.10 Submit Feedback or Complaints

An essential feature of the geoportal is the ability for users to submit feedback or complaints about their experience directly. This interactive functionality not only empowers beachgoers and stakeholders but also facilitates a responsive and adaptive management approach. Users can report issues, suggest improvements, or provide general feedback about the beach environment, amenities, or services. This direct line of communication ensures that the management authorities are informed about the public's needs and concerns in real-time, enabling more effective and timely decision-making.

Conclusion

This study has systematically explored the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in the management and development of M'diq's beaches. Through the establishment of a dedicated committee, comprehensive data collection, and the innovative design and implementation of a geoportal, we have demonstrated a multifaceted approach to sustainable beach management that balances environmental stewardship, economic interests, and public enjoyment.

The creation of the geoportal stands out as a significant advancement, offering a dynamic and interactive platform that consolidates detailed maps, environmental data, and economic license statistics. This tool not only enhances decision-making and strategic planning but also promotes transparency and public engagement. The inclusion of water quality data from the National Laboratory for Studies and Pollution Monitoring further

enriches the geoportal's utility, providing crucial insights into the health of marine ecosystems and the safety of beachgoers.

Our findings reveal a diverse range of amenities and infrastructural elements across the studied beaches, reflecting the unique characteristics and needs of each location. The analysis of water quality ratings underscores the importance of regular environmental monitoring and the need for adaptive management strategies to address areas of concern.

The methodologies and insights presented in this study contribute to the broader discourse on coastal management and GIS applications. They offer valuable lessons and frameworks that can be adapted and applied to other coastal regions facing similar challenges. As we continue to witness changes in our environmental and economic landscapes, the need for innovative, data-driven, and community-focused approaches to natural resource management becomes increasingly paramount.

This study's implications extend beyond the local context, providing a model for integrating technology, environmental science, and community engagement in coastal management practices worldwide. It is hoped that the methodologies and findings presented here will inspire further research, collaboration, and innovation in the pursuit of sustainable and resilient coastal communities.

References

1. ABDELHALEEM, F. S., BASIOUNY, M., ASHOUR, E., & MAHMOUD, A. (2021). APPLICATION OF REMOTE SENSING AND GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN IRRIGATION WATER MANAGEMENT UNDER WATER SCARCITY CONDITIONS IN FAYOUM, EGYPT. JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, 299, 113683. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2021.113683>
2. BAI, J., & PAN, W. (2022). THE CONSTRUCTION METHOD OF HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM BASED ON MOBILE NETWORK. MOBILE INFORMATION SYSTEMS, 2022, 7392478. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7392478>
3. HE, X., PERSSON, H., & ÖSTMAN, A. (2012). GEOPORTAL USABILITY EVALUATION. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SPATIAL DATA INFRASTRUCTURES RESEARCH, 7.
4. MAGUIRE, D. J., & LONGLEY, P. A. (2005). THE EMERGENCE OF GEOPORTALS AND THEIR ROLE IN SPATIAL DATA INFRASTRUCTURES. COMPUTERS, ENVIRONMENT AND URBAN SYSTEMS, 29(1), 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPENURBSYS.2004.05.012>
5. MINISTERE DE LA TRANSITION ÉNERGETIQUE, ET DU DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE, DEPARTEMENT DE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE. (2023). SURVEILLANCE DE LA QUALITE DES EAUX DE BAINNADE: RAPPORT ANALYTIQUE [ANALYTICAL REPORT ON THE MONITORING OF BATHING WATER QUALITY]. LABORATOIRE NATIONAL DES ETUDES ET DE SURVEILLANCE DE LA POLLUTION.
6. MINISTRY OF INTERIOR & MINISTRY OF EQUIPMENT, TRANSPORT, LOGISTICS, AND WATER. (2018). JOINT DIRECTIVE OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERIOR AND THE MINISTRY OF EQUIPMENT, TRANSPORT, LOGISTICS, AND WATER, DATED MAY 17, 2018.
7. RUDIANTO, SETYOHADI, D., ISDIANTO, A., & HARAHAP, K. S. (2023). COASTAL ECOSYSTEM ASSESSMENT WITH AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO LAND AND SEASCAPE COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS FOR CONSERVATION: A CASE STUDY OF THE PULO DORO COAST, MALANG REGENCY. JOURNAL OF HUNAN UNIVERSITY NATURAL SCIENCES, 50(1), 261–271. <https://doi.org/10.55463/ISSN.1674-2974.50.1.26>
8. SAEPUDIN, H., SUHARSONO, T. N., & CHALID, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR ROAD MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT APPLICATION IN BANDUNG DISTRICT. 2022 16TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON TELECOMMUNICATION SYSTEMS, SERVICES, AND APPLICATIONS (TSSA), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSSA56819.2022.10063913>
9. SATOUR, N., RAJI, O., EL MOÇAYD, N., KACIMI, I., & KASSOU, N. (2021). SPATIALIZED FLOOD RESILIENCE MEASUREMENT IN RAPIDLY URBANIZED COASTAL AREAS WITH A COMPLEX SEMI-ARID ENVIRONMENT IN NORTHERN MOROCCO. NATURAL HAZARDS AND EARTH SYSTEM SCIENCES, 21(3), 1101–1118. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-21-1101-2021>
10. SHU ZHANG. (2023). APPLICATIONS OF MARINE GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS (GIS) IN OCEAN SURVEYING. ADVANCES IN COMPUTER, SIGNALS AND SYSTEMS, 7(10). <https://doi.org/10.23977/ACSS.2023.071009>
11. ECHLOUCHI, K., OUARDOUZ, M., BERNOUSSI, A. S., & BOULAASSAL, H. (2020). SMART GEOPORTAL FOR EFFICIENT GOVERNANCE: A CASE STUDY MUNICIPALITY OF M'DIQ. IN LECTURE NOTES IN NETWORKS AND SYSTEMS (VOL. 92). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33103-0_24
12. MATA-CHINCHILLA, R., & CASTRO-CHINCHILLA, J. (2019). GEOPORTAL OF COSTA RICAN SOILS AS PUBLIC GOOD AT THE SERVICE OF THE COUNTRY. TECNOLOGIA EN MARCHA, 32(SI).
13. KEŞİK, O. A., AYDINOĞLU, A. Ç., & SAĞLAM, D. (2015). GIS BASED ACCESSIBILITY ASSESSMENT FOR PUBLIC SERVICES : ISTANBUL CASE GIS BASED ACCESSIBILITY ASSESSMENT FOR PUBLIC SERVICES : ISTANBUL CASE. FROM THE WISDOM OF THE AGES TO THE CHALLENGES OF THE MODERN WORLD, MAY 2015.
14. HAUT COMMISSARIAT AU PLAN. (2014). RECENSEMENT GENERAL DE LA POPULATION ET DE L'HABITAT.
15. DANIEL, S., & DORAN, M.-A. (2013). GEOSMARTCITY: GEOMATICS CONTRIBUTION TO THE SMART CITY. PROCEEDINGS OF THE 14TH ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DIGITAL GOVERNMENT RESEARCH, 65–71. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2479724.2479738>
16. BERNARD, L., KANELLOPOULOS, I., ANNONI, A., & SMITS, P. (2005). THE EUROPEAN GEOPORTAL - ONE STEP TOWARDS THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A EUROPEAN SPATIAL DATA INFRASTRUCTURE. COMPUTERS, ENVIRONMENT AND URBAN SYSTEMS, 29(1 SPEC.ISS.). <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPENURBSYS.2004.05.009>
17. ESRI. (2009). CREATING AND MAINTAINING A GEOPORTAL-MANAGEMENT CONSIDERATIONS. WWW.ESRI.COM